

INNOVATION HUB

CIRCULAR ECONOMY

NEFI Innovation Hubs are specialised networks led by renowned research institutions. They initiate highly relevant research and innovation projects.

Circular Economy

Target groups: all sectors, especially cement, steel, petrochemistry

Services offered by the NEFI Innovation Hubs

- NEFI Technology Talks:
A range of networking and information events
- Support throughout the entire innovation process: From project idea, application submission, to impact assessment
- Access to state-of-the-art laboratory infrastructure
- Effective dissemination and exploitation of solutions and results

The circular economy offers great potential for a climate-neutral industry. It is not only about recycling and reusing materials, but also about redesigning products and processes – with a holistic view of the entire product lifecycle right from the planning phase.

KEY FOCUS AREAS

Efficient use of resources, recycling of materials, and implementation of effective waste management strategies

Redesign of products and processes for longer lifespan and reusability

Innovative recycling methods and technologies to enhance material efficiency in industrial processes, reduce resource consumption, and minimise waste generation

CONTACT DETAILS

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HUB CO-LEADS

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